

A study plan for the research of Ms Polina Lemenkova
at the *University of Kuopio, Department of Environmental Science*
under the supervision of the Dr. Narasinha Shurpali (Senior Scientist)
the 01. September 2009 (during 3 months)

a. **Introduction** Management of environmental GIS data (Finnish ecosystems)

The proposed research aims the study and systematically organising the geographical and environmental data of the Finnish ecosystems, both terrestrial and marine (especially, shelf zone of the *Baltic Sea*) to detect the changings in the state of the Finnish ecosystems. This research will help to present systematically and to make a profound analysis of the results of ongoing environmental research of the *Biogeochemistry research group, Department of Environmental Science* in the context of the protection of the environment of the Finnish ecosystems.

Ms Lemenkova suites exactly for he proposed GIS data management research, as she has both necessary knowledge in environmental studies and in technical part of GIS-analysis and data management. She has a serious experience in marine and environmental research (having worked at the *Alfred Wegener Institut for Marine and Polar Research*, participated in the Antarctic polar expedition and having studied Arctic marine ecosystems as her Diploma work at her home University), as well as in pure cartography (GIS-analysis, satellite imageries treatment, databases management and topographic mapping during her work at the *Cadastral municipal bureau* and *Federal Space Agency* in Moscow). Therefore we support her CIMO-Scholarship application enthusiastically.

Establishment the contacts between individual scientists and strengthening the connections between the Universities is necessary nowadays for the international cooperation on the protection of the lake and terrestrial environment of the Finnish ecosystems and Baltic Sea.

b. Objectives and Aims of the research

The objective of the 3-month research period at the *University of Kouvio, Department of Environmental Science* is to realize analysing, collecting and management of geographic and environmental data of Finnish ecosystems (both terrestrial and aquatic) from different field experiments and previous projects that have been completed by the Biogeochemistry research group during the last 20 years. Organizing the data from previous GIS (Geographic Information Systems) projects into one database using MS Access and cartographic database management programme (ArcGIS 9.1, namely its part ArcCatalogue) to allow an access to the past and present data. In addition, several field expeditions are planned in the summer to research the environment of the Finnish lakes.

The ecological problems in Finland today concern the increasing pressure in the environment due to the human activities. The bioecological and chemical data, such as concentrations of the main environmental pollutants (heavy metals, pesticides, gases (CO₂, CH₄, N₂O, NO), oil concentrations, phenols and also possible radioactive concentrations) need to be studied and analysed carefully to make the prognosis of further development of the lake, forests and shelf ecosystems (at the Baltic Sea) and modelling of their possible reaction towards the human activities.

However, the most data available and already existing are very separate, uncoordinated, incomplete and set apart from each other at the present time (mostly, stored in different GIS-projects and files). There are mostly geochemical data of concentrations and balances of different pollutants (metals, gases, pesticides, etc) in the environment: in boreal, arctic terrestrial and aquatic ecosystems.

Therefore, these data cannot be studied as a whole, which does not allow to carry out proper biogeochemical investigations and profound environmental research. They need to be organizing and processing (incl. creating a table of contents similarly to the library system), which would leave a possibility for scientists to decide, what a project the data could be used for, how they correlate to each other geographically and to make an environmental analysis.

c. Working plan and methods to be applied (include a time schedule)

01.06.-15.06.2009. Data collecting and treatment

Using Arc Catalog data organising system we will assemble connections to the all existing necessary GIS data, accessing a folder on a local disk, a database on the network, or an ArcGIS Server. At this part of work the georeferencing of some data is also provided in case it is necessary (e.g. for scanned or non-referenced maps using ArcMap-inputing dataset and coordinate systems). At this part of the research the data are to be collected together to make them easier to find and to store. This part of the research can be carried out using ArcCatalog

15.06.-30.06.2009 Data management and administration

Making the data connection and the catalog of existing data is useful, as it allows an access to all the geographically referenced data from different projects to which it's linked. Together, the connections create a catalog of geographic data sources which can allow the environmentalists to use, compare and analyse promptly the necessary data for the further modelling the ecosystems.

01.07.-30.07.2009 Environmental analysis

Using the available data the environmental analysis can be proposed in a cooperation with other scientists specialized in biogeochemistry:

- ✓ Critical processes for contaminant fluxes and ecosystem behaviour
- ✓ Processes and effects in the coastal environment
- ✓ Monitoring, modelling and assessment
- ✓ History, present state and future consequences of lake contaminations

01.08.-30.08.2009 Ecological mapping and publishing one article

The results of the data analysis (July 2009) will be demonstrated in several (2-3) maps of the Finnish lakes' environment, whereas the collected data (June 2009) can be used for thematic mapping using ArcGIS 9.2. Prepared layouts will be used for publishing one paper in the scientific journal.

d. Expected results

The catalog containing environmental and geographic data Using the organised data an environmental analysis can be made (e.g. which can

be the trends and causes in the contaminants fluxes and concentrations within the ecosystems), monitoring, modelling and assessment the current situation

e. Possible use of the results

The organized library of georeferenced data will allow scientists to make an environmental analysis and modelling (e.g. which can be the):

- Modelling the ecosystem processes in the lakes of Finland
- The changes in the both terrestrial and aquatic Finnish ecosystem state (e.g. in 1980-2000 or other periods, depends upon the available data).
- Analysis the trends and causes in the contaminants' concentrations origin and ways of transport within the water of the ecosystems
- Assessment of the concentrations of gases and heavy metals in coastal, lake and marine ecosystems, modelling of its possible further distribution and transport within the net of river waters and lakes.
- Establishment of the environmental monitoring system in the Kuopio region and also at the shelf of the Baltic sea

We hope sincerely to win the CIMO-grant, as the proposed study is very actual both for the University of Kuopio as well as for the research of the Finnish lakes environment and protection in general, as the lakes ecosystems of Finland have the unique environmental importance and are the essential part of the global planet environment. Therefore, the theme of studying the ecology is very actual and challenging nowadays and we support the proposed research plan for Ms Polina Lemenkova since the 01.June 2009 until the 30.August 2009.

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Kuopio, the 27 February 2009